
INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) AND ACADEMIC LIBRARIES: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITY

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Abstract:

This paper aims to project and present an exploration of the effective utilization of information communication technology in academic libraries for the management of various library functions and providing services. In this paper researcher focused on the major barriers to implementing information communication technologies in academic libraries.

Keywords: *ICT, Library Services, Academic Libraries, explorative Management.*

Introduction:

To improve the quality of education and to make it more relevant at the different levels we are modernizing our educational system. Libraries have been considered vital components and an integral part of the entire educational system. Academic libraries have been considered as crucial for future development. The major factors can be attributed to the rapid growth and development of academic libraries providing world-class facilities and services to users, students and researchers.

Libraries and laboratories should be given more attention to improving university education in India.

Academic libraries should be better organized in terms of their collections, organization and services in particular.

The explosion of knowledge and the meteoric program of science and technology and all-out effort for importance in all knowledge fields and the consequent explosion of knowledge owing to a market level of real-time advancement

in higher education and researcher applying information communication technologies in various levels of academic and research libraries.

Importance of ICT in Academic Libraries:

Libraries have traditionally been considered as book storehouses but with rapid scientific invention particularly in information communication technologies have two important impacts as more and more information is a reality available in machine-readable form, valued is more, accurate up to date and in time. The second important thing is that today's libraries and library professionals are familiarly fast with the latest technological development to provide the best services to their users and apply different ICT tools in their regular work.

The main applications of ICT in libraries have speedily transformed the way of collection, storage and retrieval of information in academic libraries.

The digital age gave birth to new terms like digital libraries, virtual libraries, e-libraries, and libraries without walls.

Information communication technology has made a significant impact on library management and services. ICT not only changed the perspective of libraries and library issues but also made remarkable change in the users' need using ICT. Academic libraries, playing an important role in accessing global information and all types of knowledge and information resources. ICT tools are being used by students, researchers and other users to meet their educational and research demands at the right time in a smarter way.

Need of ICT in Library Services:

Latest developments in ICT have been tremendously increased the ability and possibly to access, store and process. ICT also have brought important changes in overall organization, functioning, management of services. Most of the Indian academic libraries offering second capabilities and helping to access local collections. Some libraries also using the tools to explore and exchange, flow of information.

Functions of Library with Reference to ICT:

ICT is used for – Library catalogues, Circulation system, interlibrary connection

Accessing e-resources:

Web-based reference and retrieval services organization of retrieval of

information access to online e-resources, such as e-journals, e-books and e-magazines, and e-publishing.

ICT helps to access learning resources. ICT also create greater and smarter access to information and communication through ICT tools utilised for day to day activities.

In the modern age academic libraries particularly students exploring social media for scholarly use ICT for different users such as blogs, podcasts, photo sharing, video conferencing, text talk, RSS and emails, wikis, gaming, social networking, social bookmarking.

Challenges and Opportunity:

For the effective and result-oriented implementation of ICT in libraries have to face some stumbling blocks for successful implementation of ICT for handling various library functions. Libraries and librarians face number of difficulties and challenges in providing the best services to library users there challenges are.

ICT & LIS Education:

Skilled and LIS-educated staff plays an important and significant role in providing quality library services, but in most of libraries, the staff and library professionals are not sufficient ICT skilled. They do not upgrade their knowledge while servicing the users.

As there are rapid changes in ICT solution librarians and staff should have to update their professional knowledge and skill. If most of the library staff is LIS qualified. The new LIS syllabus covers all things related to ICT in their course. The new professional is awarded about ICT and its friendly use. Mactz, M, (2008) in his study pointed out that every individual has a fear of change.

Inadequate Infrastructure:

There is a number of challenges that libraries are facing today. Libraries are facing challenges regarding physical infrastructure, lack of net connectivity, irregular supply of paper, inadequate & law configuration, PC's lack of ICT policy, worldwide useable equipment and heavy duties imported which becomes unaffordable to make a new change.

Lack of New Technologies:

There is fast growth in advancement in ICT technology, existing technology becomes outdated then libraries have to change their equipment as per the time needs which libraries cannot afford and sustain in another biggest challenge.

Lack of funds:

Funding to libraries for development is a burning issue that almost all libraries face today for the acceptance and application of new advances in ICT. Need sufficient allocation of budget but negligence and lack of importance are faced many times.

Expertise:

On the ground of technical support with regard to ICT application in libraries require a high level of expertise to apply ICT in libraries with establishment working and up to maintenance. There is lack of experts in the field of maintenance as they get higher paying jobs in other multinational or high-paying institutions to tackle these serious issues the institution is responsible for agencies in having to make provisions to arrange such trained and expert staff.

Conclusion:

The application of ICT tools and techniques has been spread all over the

world and in most of the academic libraries ICT, is being used to collect, store and disseminate information to library users due to rapid developments in the field of ICT and education field, the libraries equipped with ICT tools to serve the need of the users to provide best and fast services. With using ICT's in the library, the role of the librarian, Library professional's in-house operations has been totally changed. But as the technologies change fast libraries have to change in terms of equipment and training of ICT staff. Still, there are some challenges to libraries but can be eradicated if focused properly.

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